

Role of Digital Marketing Strategies in Promoting Consumerism in Information Technology and Communication Sector: A Case Study of Pakistan Telecommunication Company Limited

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 21, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: December 23, 2024</p> <p>Keywords : Digital Marketing Channels, Digital Marketing Strategies, Consumerism, PTCL, IT and communication sector, Digital Marketing</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14548437</p>	<p><i>The purpose of the study is to determine the role of digital marketing strategies in promoting consumerism in the IT and communication sectors while considering a case study of Pakistan Telecommunication Company Limited. A survey was conducted from 250 different customers and users of digital media. After gathering data, Smart PLS software has been used to analyse the results. The measurement and structural model through factor loading, AVE (average variance extracted), CR (composite reliability), Cronbach's alpha, discriminant validity (Fornell-Larher Criterion) and Collinearity Assessment are conducted. The hypotheses are tested through bootstrapping methods in PLS-SEM. The t-values of all path coefficients are higher than 1.96 ($p < 0.005$), which implies that relationships between digital marketing strategies, digital marketing channels and consumerism are significant at 97.5 percent confidence level. As per the partial mediation of digital marketing channels with consumerism and digital marketing strategies, it is found that the hypotheses have been accepted. Based on the findings, it can be stated that there is a significant impact of digital marketing channels and strategies on consumerism (purchase of services of PTCL). Similarly, the results confirm that digital marketing channels significantly influence digital marketing strategies.</i></p>

Introduction

Background of the Study

People are celebrating the existence of the internet in Pakistan for nearly two decades. Intuitively, it gives the sense to assume that when the customer in Pakistan becomes 'digital' and the technologies evolve, developments and behavioral improvements might occur in company marketing practices (Imtiaz et al., 2019). However, surprisingly, even though somehow the networking system is now increasingly accessible through General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) or Enhanced Data GSM Environment (EDGE) technologies everywhere. As Pakistan reaches nearly 20 billion of its people who have access to and use the internet, rather than narrowing the distance between the user and the marketer, it continues to only get larger by the day. With more than 80 broadcast channels leading to the market, more than 12 networks on the internet, over 4000 newspapers, advertisers seem resistant to the fact. Traditional marketing structures developed as it was expected by the economies of the industrial revolution.

Digital marketing is a significant component to embrace an in-demand business (Gabriel et al., 2020). Besides these, there is a comprehensive scope of digital marketing as promotion and marketing any product through electronic media is the quickest and most effective marketing tool for targeting a large market. The key to having an on-demand professional in digital marketing. Consumerism is the concept that increasing the consumption of products and services (Ruault, 2018). This may be relevant in an economic context to the primary theory that consumer spending is the main driver of the economy, and that motivating customers spend is a major policy goal.

Consumerism is a significant trend, which boosts economic growth (Choudhury, 2019; Hyder, 2016). Media marketing takes place in the form of cross-promotion and entertainment news. Video news releases that are, news reports, advertising entertainment events, goods, or media content from which the news agency or companies' owner stands to gain financial benefits (Antonio, 2019). Digital media have become dominant over the last decades, that consumers have easy access to information. Digital marketing is the promotion of digital media of goods and brands (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019; Kannan, 2017). Successful digital marketing is integrating technology with consumer behavior. Digital marketing is making the world better for marketers to catch a good market share by good market planning (Huyghe et al., 2017).

Research Aim

This study aims to determine the role of digital marketing strategies in promoting consumerism in the IT and communication sectors while considering a case study of Pakistan Telecommunication Company Limited.

Research Objectives

RO1: To analyze and figure out the concept and scope of digital marketing strategies.

RO2: To analyze and figure out the concept and scope of consumerism in information technology and communication.

RO3: To identify the connection between digital marketing strategies and consumerism.

RO4: To identify the strategies to enhance the promoting consumerism in information technology and communication.

Research Gap

Customers of this modern era are empowered, in charge of the digital media, content, and process of communication. The influence of conventional marketing strategies and communication is growing, and the consumer has no faith in the corporate brand. Technology changes the marketing environment and strategy; advertisers are constantly being forced to work in a dynamic and evolving world where they no longer have full media and message power. The purpose of selecting this specific topic is to how digital marketing strategies, identify promote consumerism in IT and communication.

Different authors such as Roberts et al., (2019) and Verhoef & Bijmolt, (2019) have worked on the digital marketing and the growth of consumerism. The studies found significant and positive results of the digital marketing channels and growth of consumers through these platforms. However, the impact of specific marketing strategies such as content marketing, email marketing, search engine optimisation, and social media marketing have not been considered. Gretzel & Mendonça (2019) considered the role of social media marketing but the study was not conducted in the IT and communication sector of Pakistan. Hence, this study would merely consider the case of PTCL, which belongs to the IT and communication sectors of Pakistan.

Research Hypothesis

Main Hypothesis: there is a significant impact of digital marketing strategies in promoting consumerism.

Sub-Hypothesis:

H1: There is a significant impact of digital marketing channels on the purchase of services of PTCL.

H2: There is a significant impact of digital marketing strategies on consumerism purchase of services of PTCL.

H3: The digital marketing channels significantly influence digital marketing strategies of PTCL.

Conceptual Framework

DV stands for the dependent variable, MV stands for mediating variable, and IV stands for the independent variable.

Significance of the Study

This study may create benefits for the marketers of Pakistan to hook a good market share. Marketers have done a lot of work to attract customers but become fail because of poor strategy (Cho et al., 2017). The strategies, which are followed in this study, may help the marketers of Pakistan. Organisations can boost their

sales by following the strategies, which discuss in this study. The success of organisations is based on marketing. However, digital media marketing creates a path clearer for marketers to become an effective tool for marketers. Also, this study discusses all these tools, which can help organisations to increase their sales performance and promote consumerism.

Research Limitations

In this study, the researcher conducts information about the role of digital marketing strategies in promoting consumerism in IT and communication of Pakistan. The limitation of the study characterized the place to find the data for the study. Moreover, the researcher used primary data for this study. An empirical study has been presumed about content marketing, pay per click marketing, social media marketing, and email marketing in digital marketing strategies. The researcher explores the past studies which are on digital marketing strategies, their effectiveness in the Pakistan context. Moreover, the researcher analyses data of consumerism for this study in the chapter of the literature review.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nawaz, (2018) investigated the research on the effect of PTCL's (Pakistan Telecommunication Company Ltd.) consumers on Goods, promotions, and sales customers. A survey questionnaire was conducted in PTCL customers. The Study sample size was 251. The study suggested that a positive effect on consumer satisfaction was observed after-sales support and promotion and goods. Moreover, the study of Holbrook, (2018) purposed the effects of sales promotion on consumer purchase behaviour in Pakistan, the Internet service provider company, from with a survey of 150 Lahore web users, reported that sales promotional practices have a significant effect on customer interest and shift consumer buying behaviour. The promotion strategy has been a legitimate way of improving the revenue and winning market position. The promotion of sales is indeed a preferred approach to draw consumer interest other than the internet advertisements and campaigns.

Additionally, the study of Palwasha, (2016) has focused on the influence of online to offline (o2o) trade service brand loyalty and brand recognition on customer loyalty and repeated intention to buy. The collection of data took the shape of a questionnaire using a survey instrument. It has been proposed that the optimistic brand image greatly influences repeat buying. Even when consumers get the value through which their desires, aspirations, and expectations are fulfilled, they are satisfied. In a similar study done by Malik & Khan, (2020), it was found that the drivers that shape customer satisfaction in Pakistan's telecommunications industry are also not confined exclusively to trust. They could also be identified by interaction with social categories like youth and gender.

Whereas, Yuan et al., (2019) investigated the purchase behaviour of consumers at Pakistan Telecommunication Limited Company (PTCL) and identified that the company comprises 96 percent of customers to fixed local networks. The authors did not focus on the role of digital marketing channels and any digital strategies. It serves as a landline industry dominance but faces slow growth over the last 8 years. The author reused primary data collected from PTCL landline customers through a well-structured questionnaire. The study suggested that the company may concentrate on providing a service in surrounding urban areas, implementing wireless sensor network mobile phone connections, providing affordable and economical packages for landline users, offering creative and reliable in-sales services to its landline consumers to recapture the market. Moreover, BANNU, (2018) has found in the study of evaluating Ecommerce customer loyalty indicators for PTCL's management perspective. It implies that customer satisfaction is rising significantly to Ecommerce factors that concentrate on key consumers, coordinate across Ecommerce, manage information, and integrate e-commerce technology, and the findings relate significantly to the study in which the majority of e-commerce users and management roles either have acknowledged strongly agree.

It has been described by Ćikić & Veselinović, (2019) that digital marketing plays a significant role in every company's marketing campaign inclusive of its industry, size, or country of origin. The research conducted in the UK, using a sample of 200 participants, indicated that the key aspect of electronic marketing is influence on the purchasing decisions, which is an organic marketing technique, based on the intimate association between the company and its targets or clients that have willingly demonstrated their stake in the company's goods. Moreover, the study conducted in Pakistan by Veltsos, (2017) identified the impact of digital marketing on the growth of consumerism. The sample of 250 respondents has confirmed that the future of digital marketing would be focused on how advertisers build ways to juggle modern and conventional media altogether in a great market-driven fix.

However, the study of Zaefarian et al., (2020) spreading international consumerism, the influence of mass media, and attention on Chinese consumer principles. It has found that access to consumer and Western media material and advertising leads to a readier recognition of the 2 consumerist ideals. Additionally, the study of (Klas, 2016) based on consumerism, and the idea of social marketing. One of the three experimental conditions was systematically allocated to participants (N = 252, residing in Australia). It verified that organic identity could be programmed to establish identity-congruent changes towards organic consumption.

Eleboda, (2017) evaluated the sales marketing activities of established developed world consumer goods firms. The research was performed in Turkey with a broad population sample of 400. It reported that sales promotions are becoming increasingly relevant in Turkish companies' overall promotional practices, although there are variations in their usage by the form of industry, business scale, service area, and signifier of company decision-making. Consequently, the study of (Petrescu & Lauer, 2017) examined a glimpse at post-purchase behaviour and consumerism. Business leaders increasingly consider network marketing as a potential business. Pakistan's study has verified that the marketing approach has been mistaken as a getting rich quick scheme, and it is also popular for channel marketers around the globe to respond to their business' legality and reliability.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Nature of Methods

The nature of this study is confirmed. In the confirmatory study, the researcher checks the credibility of the hypothesis, which has been produced, known as a categorical hypothesis (Forthmann et al., 2019). This indicates that previous research on the subject may have been worked out and some findings have been published. There are two types of research methods, quantitative and qualitative. Quantitative data are statistical and are usually standardized in nature, which means they are linear and more organized.

This type of data is calculated using figures and values, making it a more appropriate candidate to evaluate the data. However, qualitative data are non-statistical by design, and are usually informal or non-structured (Gibbs, 2019). This data is not generally calculated using the specific numbers used for graph and chart growth. It is defined instead based on attributes, characteristics, marks, and other identification. This study was primarily quantitative, in which the researcher asks survey questions from different customers to identify the role of digital marketing strategies in promoting consumerism in IT and technology.

Research Approach

The research approach is a plan, a procedure that consists of the step in collecting the data, analysis, and interpretation (Tuffour, 2017). There are two types of research approach, inductive research, and deductive study. In deductive research, the researcher conducts the answer of participants in the form of numbering, which means quantitative. This study is deductive, in which the researcher gets data from the participant with the resource of the survey questionnaire.

Data Collection Methods

Data collection is the process of gathering and measuring the data on targeted establishment systems. However, there are two major types of data collection, which are given below.

Primary Data Collection Methods

Primary data is an author's first-hand approach to results, with methods involving surveys, interviews, or experiments (Frederiks et al., 2016). It is compiled directly from primary sources, because of the analysis plan. Primary data is even more accurate because it is obtained directly from a specific population. Moreover, other types of primary data include focus groups, observations, and oral histories. In this study, the researcher adopted the primary data collection method, which becomes efficient for the study.

Secondary Data Collection Methods

Secondary data is a segment of data obtained by someone other than the researcher (Johnston, 2017). General sources of secondary data include data from censuses, departmentally collected state information, and corporate documents. Also, the data that was collected initially for other purposes of investigation. The secondary data sources are extremely easily accessible. However, the researcher did not adopt the secondary data collection method because of the nature of the study.

Sample and Population

The researcher has chosen 250-sample size, which is good enough to identify the impact of digital marketing strategies on consumption. However, the population of this research will be different customers and the users of digital media, which will be more effective for the researcher to identify the relevant information.

Research Ethics

According to Quinlan et al., (2019), the researcher must obey the ethics of research in any study; else, it would have a negative influence on the respondents of this study. Every researcher needs it to maintain ethical standards in the procedure of data collection. Moreover, the confidentiality of any respondents is a primary concern for the researcher. However, when the ethical code is not met in the study, respondents have not filled out the survey. The researcher must protect the participants' information, instead of being harmful to the study.

Data Analysis Procedures

The process of data analysis is most essential in the study. The study is completely based on data analysis. However, when this procedure has functioned with efficiency, and the findings become similar, the study would be valued. Smart PLS software has been considered for analysing the results obtained from the survey. Validity, reliability and path coefficient test have been examined with the help of this software.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results from the measurement model and structure model analysis has been given below:

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

The measurement and structural model have been analysed by using PLS-SEM with the help of Smart PLS (Cepeda-Carrion et al., 2019).

Measurement Model Assessment

In order to assess the measurement model, factor loading, AVE (average variance extracted), CR (composite reliability), Cronbach's alpha and discriminant validity were examined (Cepeda-Carrion et al., 2019).

Factor loading

The factor loading has been illustrated by the items in table 1. As shown in Table 1, all indicators measuring a respective construct are greater than 0.50 (Islami et al., 2020). Therefore, the validity of constructs is confirmed.

Table 1: Factor loading

	CONSUMERISM	DMC	DMS
C1	0.730	0.437	0.351
C2	0.782	0.443	0.437
C3	0.787	0.453	0.438
C4	0.762	0.405	0.382
C5	0.798	0.464	0.465
C6	0.708	0.395	0.375
C7	0.791	0.479	0.459
C8	0.755	0.546	0.471
DMC1	0.413	0.756	0.406
DMC2	0.492	0.738	0.464
DMC3	0.472	0.785	0.483
DMC4	0.434	0.776	0.483
DMC5	0.490	0.836	0.540
DMC6	0.489	0.815	0.562
DMC7	0.464	0.760	0.509
DMS1	0.491	0.553	0.811
DMS2	0.357	0.427	0.754
DMS3	0.371	0.454	0.725
DMS4	0.347	0.467	0.734
DMS5	0.380	0.432	0.732
DMS6	0.371	0.418	0.703
DMS7	0.446	0.463	0.759
DMS8	0.378	0.460	0.744
DMS9	0.539	0.546	0.750

Construct Validity and Reliability

The Composite Reliability is higher than 0.70 and AVE values are higher than 0.5 in all constructs (Sujati, & Akhyar, 2020). Additionally, Cronbach's Alpha values are more than 0.8, which are considered excellent (Taber, 2018). Thus, all the values are considered reliable.

Table 2: Construct Validity and Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
CONSUMERISM	0.898	0.902	0.918	0.585
DMC	0.894	0.896	0.916	0.611

DMS	0.901	0.905	0.919	0.557
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Discriminant Validity

The discriminant validity was measured in accordance with the Fornell-Larcker Criterion. According to this criterion, the square root of the AVE should be greater than the correlation among the constructs (Sujati, & Akhyar, 2020). The measurement model demonstrated acceptable discriminant validity, as the square root of AVE (values off-diagonal in bold) are higher than the correlations in the respective columns and rows.

Table 3: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	CONSUMERISM	DMC	DMS
CONSUMERISM	0.765		
DMC	0.597	0.782	
DMS	0.557	0.634	0.746

The result shows that all the three constructs of DMC (Direct Marketing Channel), DMS (Direct Marketing Strategies) and Consumerism are valid measures as per their estimated parameters (see figure 01 and table 2). In addition, they are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 1: Measurement Model Assessment

Structural Model Assessment

For examining the relationship between digital marketing channels, digital marketing strategies and consumerism, the structural model has been assessed (Fani et al., 2019). For the assessment of inner model, firstly, path coefficients of the relationship are observed and their significance is tested through the bootstrapping method.

Coefficient of determination (R-value)

Table 4 shows that the R^2 value is 0.409 for consumerism. It indicates 40.9 per cent consumerism is influenced by digital marketing channel (Sujati, & Akhyar, 2020). In addition, 40.2 per cent of digital marketing channels are affected by consumerism.

Table 4: Coefficient of Determination

	R Square
CONSUMERISM	0.409
DMC	0.402

Model Fit Measures

In the SEM-PLS, the fitness of the model is referred to the various measures like SRMR (standardised root-mean-square residual), d_{ULS} , d_G , NFI (Normed Fit Index) and Chi-square. In the table below, the values of both saturated and estimated model are presented. The

saturated model evaluates the correlation among all constructs, while the estimated model is based upon the total effect scheme.

Table 5: Model Fit Summary

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.058	0.058
d_ULS	0.998	0.998
d_G	0.371	0.371
Chi-Square	51.31	51.13
NFI	0.852	0.852

Collinearity Assessment (VIF)

Table 6 presents the VIF values. All values are acceptable as the VIF values are lower than 5.

Table 6: Collinearity Statistics (VIF)

	CONSUMERISM	DMC	DMS
CONSUMERISM			
DMC	1.672		
DMS	1.672	1.000	

Hypothesis Testing

After analysing measurement mode, a structural model was analysed (Chin et al., 2020). In this process, hypotheses of the research are tested through bootstrapping methods in PLS-SEM. The t-values of all path coefficients are higher than 1.96 ($p < 0.005$), which implies that relationships are significant at 97.5 per cent confidence level.

Table 7: Hypothesis Testing

		Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
DMC	->	0.407	0.411	0.066	6.214	0.000
CONSUMERISM						
DMS	->	0.298	0.297	0.070	4.243	0.000
CONSUMERISM						
DMS -> DMC		0.634	0.638	0.050	12.771	0.000

Figure 2: Measurement Model Assessment

As per the results of the values t-statistics and p-values in the partial mediation of digital marketing channels, it is noted that the hypotheses have been accepted (Chin et al., 2020). Based on the results, it can be stated that there is a significant impact of digital marketing channels on consumerism (purchase of services of PTCL). There is a significant impact of digital marketing strategies on consumerism (purchase of services of PTCL). Similarly, the results confirm that digital marketing channels significantly influence digital marketing strategies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS/IMPLICATIONS

Conclusion

Technology has shaped marketing practices and consumer behaviour in general. In particular, with the development of new advances in interconnected information and concentrated life-worlds filled with technology, technology has become inextricably linked with marketing procedures and forms of consumption in the IT and communication sector of Pakistan. In this regard, the study aim was to determine the role of digital marketing strategies in promoting consumerism in the IT and communication sectors while considering a case study of Pakistan Telecommunication Company Limited. It has been concluded that in Pakistan, the constant separation of technology from marketing and consumption would virtually destroy the very fabric of modern business and everyday life.

The study concluded that in Pakistan, digital marketing has taken on a much more significant role and importance in promoting consumerism in information technology and communication sector. There is no doubt or debate that technology has changed marketing. Most organisations in the IT and communication sector like PTCL have built websites and maintain normal and ongoing customer relationships through different digital marketing channels such as email, weblogs, smartphones apps, and various social media platforms. More and more independent companies communicate with representatives as consumers via mobile phones and PCs over the Internet. In the communication sector, organisations like PTCL has a digital platform that showcases their elements and provides various digital marketing tools for their customers. However, the use of social media to gain consumer attention has shown an immense effect on consumer purchase behaviour.

On the other hand, the study also highlighted that in Pakistan, digital marketing strategy such as content marketing has shown an increase in sales and consumption, which is same in the case of PTCL customers. Therefore, it has been concluded that content marketing is changing the buying behaviour of people of Pakistan. Apart from this, in the case of PTCL in Pakistan, PPC also played a significant role in attracting customers. Additionally, it has been found that PPC has shown a significant positive change in the behaviour of customers that organisations pay per click marketing to improve the service of their product, which they are well aware of people come to a website to make money, which mostly benefits to the organisation.

Regarding the impact on consumerism and digital marketing, in Pakistan, social media marketing has been concluded to be remarkable digital marketing strategy due to the playing crucial role in digital marketing. Consequently, the study results concluded that in Pakistan, digital marketing strategies play an important role and there is a significant relationship between digital marketing strategies and channels in promoting consumerism.

Implications for PTCL

In Pakistan, the number of social media users has been continuing to increase every day and it has been predicted to rise by up to 26 per cent. In this regard, social media has been considered among the most remarkable factors for the organisations in the IT and communication sector to gain consumer intention. Therefore, PTCL is recommended to build an effective social media marketing strategy in order to build brand awareness for their goods and services.

Through Social Media Marketing (SMM), PTCL can use direct and person-to-person communication to achieve out to strongly target potential customers in Pakistan. However, to take advantage of these social media opportunities, marketers at PTCL must acquire new abilities and skills, in particular, using social media for adequate communication with consumers, as well as for advertising and promoting their products and administration. Besides, the research findings revealed an ‘opportunity hole’ among advertisers in Pakistan that are thwarting efforts by organisations to transform content marketing from a promising set of research into a flexible, versatile and core business potential. Therefore, to bridge this significant gap, PTCL advertisers should learn or acquire new skills in order to be able to demonstrate to the consumer that they can leverage new media.

Implications for Managers

It has been recommended that the manager should be mindful of the above digital marketing elements affecting their consumers and apply appropriate procedures in their digital marketing efforts. However, managers are recommended to use a holistic approach to meet consumer needs and leverage the open doors that are available in the digital marketing phase by identifying the variables that affect them across different digital marketing channels.

In Pakistan, with the exponential growth of the number of web clients in recent years, it is clear that the level of digital marketing is enormous. For the manager to move towards this emerging business sector, they need to understand the environment in which their customers live, how they think and how they are changing with the increased use of technology in their day to day operations. All things considered, a positive consumerist approach should be adopted by the manager. Considering that the manager needs to implement smart digital marketing strategies that are fully aligned with consumer needs to unlock great opportunities. In this regard, the manager may gain insight into customer perceptions by following conversations on social networks and product review pages and taking the opportunity to react and create dialogue.

Future Work

The research is limited to the Information Technology and Communication sector, in the future work, the research can be replicated to other sectors as well. The research has followed particular geographical limitation, as it is carried out in Pakistan only. However, the research can be conducted in other countries as well, in order to explore the impact of digital marketing on consumerism. Further, in future work, the research can adopt a qualitative research methodology approach for analysing the different view of respondents about the impact of digital marketing practices on their purchasing behaviour.

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